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**Summary of Human and Animal Anthrax
Surveillance Capacity in South Africa and
Mozambique 2024**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Anthrax (*Bacillus anthracis*) is an emerging infectious disease listed by the US National Institute for Allergy and Infectious Diseases as a Category A priority disease. Yet, concern regarding the disease potential and public health threat of this bacterial zoonosis is quite variable among countries and communities.

In this desk assessment, we document the resources, methods, governance, and reporting structure for surveillance of anthrax in humans and animals in South Africa and Mozambique. These adjoining countries share the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area, are home to wild ungulates and livestock susceptible to the disease, and are in an anthrax-endemic zone. The primary difference between these countries is economic: South Africa's gross domestic product (**GDP**) is the equivalent of over \$1.3 trillion, while Mozambique's GDP is \$44 billion. Both countries strive to adhere to the International Health Regulations and have surveillance measures in place. The degree to which surveillance measures are followed in each country is impossible to fully evaluate in a desk assessment. There is published evidence, documented in this report, that Mozambique's surveillance capacity is insufficient by international standards set, for instance, by the Centers for Disease Control (**CDC**) and the World Health Organization (**WHO**). To better understand the capacity of these countries for appropriate anthrax surveillance, this report will be followed by a questionnaire and interview of zoonotic disease/anthrax subject matter experts from each country.

ABBREVIATIONS

APE	Agents Program Multipurpose Elementary
ARC	Agricultural Research Council
CDC	Centers for Disease Control
CSA	Community Surveillance Agents
DALRRD	Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development
DG	Director General
DINAV	National Directorate of Veterinary Services
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FAVET	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine
FELTP	Field Epidemiology and Laboratory Training Programme
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IDSR	CDC's Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response Program
INIP	National Fish Inspection Institute
KNP	Kruger National Park
MADER	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
MASA	Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security
MIMAIP	Ministry of Sea, Inland Waters, Fisheries
MISAU	Ministry of Health
NAHF	National Animal Health Forum
NHLS	National Health Laboratory Services
NICD	National Institute for Communicable Diseases
NMNH	National Museum of Natural History
NPHI	National Public Health Institute
NRF	National Research Foundation
OBP	Onderstepoort Biological Products
OVR	Office of Veterinary Research
PVS	Provincial Veterinary Service
SANParks	South African National Parks
SAVC	South African Veterinary Council
SIS-HOSP	Hospital Management System
SIS-ROH	Death Registration Information System
SIVE	Epidemiological Surveillance Information System
SVO	State Veterinary Office
UEM	Eduardo Mondlane University
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VS	Veterinary Service
WHO	World Health Organization
WOAH	World Organization of Animal Health

SOUTH AFRICA

1. Overview

South Africa is a mixed economy, upper-middle income country by global standards. The country has established surveillance systems to monitor anthrax activity and detect outbreaks in both animal and human populations. These systems rely on reporting mechanisms from veterinary clinics, livestock farmers, wildlife authorities, and healthcare facilities to identify suspected cases of anthrax promptly. Communication channels and reporting protocols are in place to ensure timely dissemination of information about anthrax outbreaks between veterinary authorities, public health agencies, laboratory networks, and relevant stakeholders to coordinate response efforts and implement control measures effectively. South Africa invests in research and training initiatives to enhance understanding of anthrax epidemiology, diagnostic methods, and control strategies. Veterinary professionals receive ongoing training on anthrax surveillance, diagnosis, and outbreak response to maintain competency and preparedness. Overall, South Africa's current capacity for reporting and diagnosing anthrax is robust, supported by well-equipped laboratories, established surveillance systems, collaboration between veterinary and public health authorities, and ongoing efforts to improve knowledge and skills in anthrax detection and control.

2. Resources for surveillance of anthrax in animals in South Africa

2.1 Department of Agriculture, Land Reform & Rural Development, Government of South Africa (DALRRD)¹

The DALRRD oversees the implementation of agricultural policies and regulations, including those related to animal health and disease control. Within the department, the Directorate of Animal Health is responsible for implementing measures to prevent, monitor, and control infectious diseases in animals. Under the Directorate of Animal Health, Veterinary Services functions and responsibilities are organized by province and state. The Directorate of Animal Health functions and responsibilities include:

Animal disease control: develops and implements disease programs for livestock, poultry, and wildlife.

Veterinary public health: ensures the safety of animal products to prevent the transmission of zoonotic disease through inspection and certification processes.

International trade: facilitates international trade in animals and animal products; establishes protocols for the import and export of animals, including requirements related to disease testing and certification.

Emergency response: coordinates response efforts in the event of disease outbreaks or emergencies, including surveillance, containment, and vaccination campaigns.

Under the Directorate of Animal Health, South Africa's Veterinary Services are responsible for overseeing animal health and disease control measures, including anthrax surveillance and response. Veterinary professionals are trained to recognize the clinical signs of anthrax in animals, collect appropriate samples, and collaborate with laboratory facilities for diagnosis. Anthrax is a significant concern in South Africa, especially in agricultural areas where livestock farming is prevalent. The South African Veterinary Services play a crucial role in the control and management of anthrax outbreak through:

Surveillance and monitoring, including:

Surveillance: monitoring livestock populations for anthrax, particularly in areas with a history of anthrax outbreaks.

Diagnostic testing: Veterinary professionals collect and analyze or submit samples from suspected anthrax cases to veterinary diagnostic laboratories.

Epidemiological investigation: investigate outbreaks to determine the extent of the outbreak, identify affected animals, and trace potential sources of infection.

Vaccination programs, including:

Preventive vaccination: implement vaccination programs for livestock, a key strategy for reducing the incidence of anthrax and preventing outbreaks.

Strategic vaccination: conduct targeted or mass vaccination campaigns in high-risk areas or during periods of heightened anthrax activity.

Control measures, including:

Quarantine and movement restrictions: impose quarantine measures and movement restrictions on farms or areas affected by anthrax.

Culling and disposal: recommend or implement the culling and proper disposal of affected to prevent the spread of anthrax spores.

Public awareness and education, including

Information dissemination: collaborate with farmers, livestock owners, and the public to raise awareness about anthrax, its signs and symptoms, and preventive measures.

Training: provide training to veterinary professionals and livestock handlers on anthrax recognition, proper sample collection, and biosecurity measures.

Research and collaboration, including

Research initiatives: support research efforts to better understand anthrax epidemiology, transmission dynamics, and factors influencing outbreaks.

Collaboration with stakeholders: collaborate with government agencies, academic institutions, industry stakeholders, and international organizations to coordinate anthrax control efforts, share information, and implement best practices.

International reporting and compliance:

WOAH reporting: report anthrax outbreaks and adhere to international guidelines for control and prevention.

Cross-border cooperation: engage in cooperation and information sharing with neighboring countries to address transboundary anthrax risks and facilitate coordinated responses to outbreaks that may affect multiple jurisdictions.

Each province in South Africa has its own Provincial Veterinary Service (**PVS**), which operates under the authority of the provincial Department of Agriculture. The PVS is responsible for implementing animal health programs, disease surveillance, and regulatory enforcement within its jurisdiction. PVS offices are typically located in major towns or cities within each province and serve as regional hubs for veterinary activities. State Veterinary Offices (**SVO**) are regional veterinary offices that fall under the umbrella of the PVS. SVOs are responsible for providing veterinary services, disease control measures, and regulatory oversight within specific districts or regions. State veterinarians and vet technicians are employed within the state veterinary system and are mandated to engage in a variety of activities such as: a) conducting

routine inspections of livestock farms, slaughterhouses, and animal products facilities to ensure compliance with health and safety standards; responding to disease outbreaks, aiding with animal health, quarantine, and movement restriction; coordinating vaccination programs; collaborating with other government agencies, research institutions, and industry stakeholders to address emerging animal health challenges and promote sustainable agriculture; and collaborating with organizations such as the National Institute for Communicable Diseases (**NICD**) and the Agricultural Research Council (**ARC**) to help strengthen disease surveillance, research, and capacity-building efforts.

[2.2 South African National Parks \(SANParks\)²](#)

Anthrax is endemic in the northern part of Kruger National Park (**KNP**). Anthrax surveillance and research are active in this area. South African National Parks (**SANParks**) is the parastatal organ responsible for managing KNP and is the primary stakeholder overseeing wildlife conservation and health management within the park. KNP's management team, which includes park managers, conservation officers, and ecologists, plays a key role in decision-making related to wildlife health management and disease control measures. The state veterinary office within KNP forms part of national veterinary services (under the governance of the Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development - **DALRRD**) which is mandated to provide medical care to wildlife, conduct disease surveillance, and implement disease management and control strategies. This also includes the maintenance of hard borders (fences) of the KNP as an essential disease control measure. State veterinary services work in tandem with SANParks veterinary wildlife services who are mandated to maintain wildlife health and conservation. Collaborations with research institutions and universities provide expertise, resources, and funding for wildlife health research, disease surveillance, and monitoring programs in KNP.

SANParks conducts media releases alerting the public to anthrax outbreaks and posts [Forums](#), [Announcements](#) and other important wildlife information, including publications on anthrax ecology in wildlife on its website.

[2.3 National Animal Health Forum \(NAHF\)³](#)

Established in 2006 by a group of concerned veterinarians and animal production groups, the National Animal Health Forum (**NAHF**) provides opportunities for liaising with the government regarding animal disease control matters. The goal of this public-private partnership is to improve veterinary services and compliance with animal health standards by meeting regularly with DALRRD. The NAHF website provides a list of controlled and notifiable animal diseases. Anthrax is a controlled disease in South Africa. The website also hosts the [Animal Disease Reporting Manual](#)²⁵ and describes the procedure for disease reporting by provincial veterinary services to the Directorate of Animal Health. The Manual describes only the requirements for disease information at a national level, pointing out that provincial requirements may be more stringent. A variety of data is required by the National Directorate of Animal Health in the case of an animal disease outbreak, including:

- Month, provincial code state veterinary area code, local municipality (district) code, disease code, and species code.
- Farm ID, geographic location (GPS location).
- Number of susceptible animals (at risk from the affected animal).
- Number of outbreaks, number of cases, number of deaths, number killed or slaughtered, number treated, number vaccinated.

in his area. This report must then be authorized by the provincial director and submitted to the national Sub-directorate of Epidemiology. The Act requires that all occurrences of controlled and notifiable diseases be reported to the national directorate. Animal health technicians of the area must also inform the state vet of outbreaks of diseases where the involvement of the state vet was not necessary. Finally, the World Organization of Animal Health (**WOAH**) requires member countries to report on all listed OIE diseases (including anthrax).

[2.5 South African Veterinary Council \(SAVC\)⁵](#)

The South African Veterinary Council (**SAVC**) is the regulatory body for veterinary professionals in South Africa. It ensures that veterinarians adhere to professional standards and ethical practices in the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of animal diseases, including infectious diseases. The SAVC licenses veterinarians, accredits veterinary training institutions, and monitors continuing education requirements to maintain professional competency. These institutions collaborate with the Department of Health, NICD, and other stakeholders to address zoonotic diseases and mitigate the risk of infectious disease transmission between animals and humans. Their efforts contribute to the overall health and well-being of both animal populations and human communities in South Africa.

[2.6 Agricultural Research Council⁶](#)

The ARC is a research institution focused on agricultural systems and economic development. It conducts research into animal health, genetics, nutrition, and production systems to enhance the productivity and sustainability of South Africa's agricultural sector. The ARC collaborates with government agencies, universities, and industry stakeholders to address infectious diseases affecting livestock and other animals.

[2.7 Agricultural Research Council-Office of Veterinary Research \(ARC-OVR\)⁷](#)

The Office of Veterinary Research (**OVR**) is a flagship campus of the ARC primarily responsible for diagnostics and research related to the health and welfare status of herds and wildlife in South Africa. All diagnostics related to controlled diseases are confirmed and reported through the ARC-OVR. The OVR is the collaborating center for the WOAHS surveillance and control of animal diseases in Africa as well as the Food and Agriculture Organization (**FAO**) of the United Nations for the emergency preparedness for transboundary animal diseases for Africa. The ARC-OVR provides anthrax diagnosis via PCR identification from culture, and produces vaccines, including anthrax vaccine.

[2.8 Onderstepoort Biological Products \(OBP\)⁸](#)

Onderstepoort Biological Products (**OBP**) is a South African company that plays a significant role in anthrax control efforts. It manufactures anthrax vaccines for use in livestock, particularly in regions where anthrax is endemic. OBP also conducts research to improve existing anthrax vaccines and develop new methods for anthrax prevention and control. This includes studying vaccine efficacy, safety, and optimal vaccination strategies. Collaboration with government agencies responsible for animal health and agriculture is another key aspect of OBP's role. It provides technical expertise, supplies vaccines, and supports vaccination campaigns to control anthrax outbreaks. Additionally, OBP provides training and capacity building initiatives to veterinarians, animal health workers, and farmers on anthrax prevention, detection, and control measures. This helps ensure effective implementation of control strategies at the grassroots level. In emergency situations, OBP plays a crucial role in responding to anthrax outbreaks by supplying vaccines and

assisting in emergency vaccination campaigns. This rapid response helps contain outbreaks and minimize their impact on livestock and human populations. Furthermore, OBP contributes to public awareness and education campaigns about anthrax, its risks, and preventive measures. This helps raise awareness among livestock owners and communities, promoting early detection and timely response to anthrax outbreaks. Overall, OBP is instrumental in anthrax control efforts through vaccine production, research, collaboration, training, emergency response, and public awareness initiatives.

2.9 The Onderstepoort Faculty of Veterinary Science, University of Pretoria⁹

The Faculty of Veterinary Science at the University of Pretoria plays a significant role in the control and management of anthrax. The faculty conducts cutting-edge research on anthrax, exploring various aspects of the disease, including its epidemiology, transmission dynamics, and host-pathogen interactions. This research generates valuable insights that inform effective control strategies. Onderstepoort Veterinary Faculty offers state-of-the-art diagnostic services for anthrax detection. Through advanced laboratory techniques and expertise, they provide accurate and timely diagnosis of anthrax cases in animals, facilitating prompt intervention and control measures.

The faculty is involved in the development and production of anthrax vaccines for animals. These vaccines are crucial for immunizing susceptible livestock species, such as cattle, sheep, and goats, thereby preventing outbreaks and reducing the risk of transmission to humans. Onderstepoort Veterinary Faculty actively participates in anthrax surveillance and monitoring programs. By monitoring disease trends and identifying high-risk areas, they contribute to early detection, rapid response, and targeted control interventions. The faculty conducts training programs and workshops for veterinarians, animal health professionals, and relevant stakeholders involved in anthrax control. These capacity-building initiatives enhance knowledge and skills in anthrax diagnosis, prevention, and control measures. Onderstepoort Veterinary Faculty collaborates with governmental agencies, research institutions, and international organizations to strengthen anthrax control efforts. These collaborations foster information sharing, resource mobilization, and coordinated action for effective disease management.

In the event of anthrax outbreaks, the faculty provides emergency response support, including rapid deployment of veterinary teams, provision of vaccines, and implementation of containment measures. This swift response helps mitigate the spread of the disease and minimize its impact on animal and public health. Onderstepoort Veterinary Faculty engages in public awareness campaigns and educational initiatives to raise awareness about anthrax among livestock owners, farmers, and communities. By promoting preventive measures and early reporting of suspected cases, they contribute to disease control and prevention efforts. Overall, the Onderstepoort Veterinary Faculty plays a crucial role in anthrax control through its multifaceted approach, encompassing research, diagnostics, vaccine development, surveillance, capacity building, collaboration, emergency response, and public education.

Summary of animal disease resources in South Africa from the South African National Animal Health Forum, with relevance to anthrax

Name of Institution	Type of Institution	Location	Role in Anthrax Surveillance
Department of Agriculture, Land Reform, and Rural Development (DALRRD)	Government	Pretoria	Overall coordination of anthrax surveillance efforts, veterinary oversight
National Institute for Communicable Diseases (NICD)- special pathogens unit	Government	Johannesburg	Surveillance and analysis of anthrax cases in humans for the SADC region*
Wildlife and Environmental Health Surveillance Unit	Non-Government	Cape Town, Johannesburg, Durban, Bloemfontein, East London, Pietermaritzburg, Port Elizabeth, Pretoria, Nelspruit, Kimberley, Polokwane, Mafikeng	Surveillance of anthrax cases in wildlife and environmental health
National and Provincial Veterinary Services	Government	Various provinces in South Africa	Surveillance, reporting, and investigation of anthrax cases in animals and disease control strategies
Provincial Departments of Health	Government	Various provinces in South Africa	Surveillance, reporting, and investigation of anthrax cases in humans
South African Veterinary Association (SAVA)	Non-Government	Nationwide	Advocacy, support, and information dissemination related to anthrax surveillance
Onderstepoort Veterinary Institute	Government	Pretoria	Laboratory confirmation and analysis of anthrax cases in animals
National Health Laboratory Service (NHLS)	Government	Various locations across South Africa	Laboratory confirmation and analysis of anthrax cases in humans
Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratories	Non-Government	Various locations across South Africa	Laboratory confirmation and analysis of anthrax cases in animals
Epidemiology Units	Government	Various provinces in South Africa	Data analysis and epidemiological investigation of anthrax cases

Research Institutions (e.g., Universities)	Government	Nationwide	Research on anthrax epidemiology, diagnosis, and control
Wildlife Research Organizations	Non-Governmental	Kruger National Park (Mpumalanga, Limpopo), Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park (Northern Cape)	Research and surveillance of anthrax in wildlife
National Department of Health	Government	Pretoria	Policy development and coordination of anthrax surveillance efforts
South African National Parks (SANParks)	Government/parastatal	Various national parks (Kruger National Park, Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park, Addo Elephant National Park, Hluhluwe-iMfolozi Park, Table Mountain National Park)	Surveillance and management of anthrax in wildlife within national parks
Wildlife Conservation Organizations	Non-Governmental	Various locations across South Africa	Advocacy, support, and management of anthrax surveillance efforts in wildlife
Veterinary Training Institutions (e.g., University Veterinary Faculties)	Government and non-governmental	Pretoria	Education and training of veterinarians on anthrax surveillance and control
Human Health Training Institutions (e.g., Medical Schools)	Government	Nationwide	Education and training of human health professionals on anthrax surveillance and control
Wildlife and Environmental Education Centers	Non-Governmental	Various locations across South Africa	Public awareness and education on anthrax surveillance and prevention
National Research Foundation (NRF)	Government	Pretoria	Funding and support for research on anthrax surveillance and control
Wildlife Research Centers	Non-Governmental	Various locations across South Africa	Research and surveillance of anthrax in wildlife

*The Southern African Development Community (SADC) is a Regional Economic Community comprising 16 Member States; Angola, Botswana, Comoros, Democratic Republic of Congo, Eswatini, Lesotho, Madagascar, Malawi, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Seychelles, South Africa, United Republic of Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

Summary of reporting resources in South Africa, with relevance to anthrax

Stage	Government Institutions	Non-Governmental Institutions	Stakeholders
Data Collection	Department of Agriculture, Land Reform, and Rural Development (DALRRD) - Pretoria; National Institute for Communicable Diseases (NICD) - Johannesburg		Veterinarians, livestock farmers, wildlife managers, public health officials, laboratory professionals
Reporting	Provincial Veterinary Services Provincial Departments of Health	SA Veterinary Association - Nationwide	Veterinary Services of DALRRD, NICD, provincial and municipal veterinary services
Case Verification	Onderstepoort Veterinary Institute – Pretoria National Health Laboratory Service (NHLS) - Nationwide	Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratories - Various locations	Veterinary laboratories (e.g., Onderstepoort Veterinary Institute), veterinary diagnostic experts, epidemiologists
Data Analysis	Epidemiology Units - Various provinces Research Institutions - Nationwide	Wildlife research organizations - Various locations	Epidemiologists, public health analysts, veterinary epidemiology units, research institutions
Surveillance Coordination	National Department of Health - Pretoria; South Africa National Parks (SANParks) - Various national parks		DALRRD National Department of Health SANParks Provincial conservation departments
Response Planning	Provincial and Municipal Governments - Various provinces and municipalities in South Africa; Department of Environmental Affairs - Pretoria		Veterinary services, public health agencies, wildlife management authorities, provincial and municipal governments
Capacity Building	Veterinary Training Institutions (University Veterinary Faculty) -Human Health Training Institutions (e.g., Medical Schools) - Nationwide	Wildlife and Environmental Education Centers - Various locations across South Africa	Veterinary associations (e.g., South African Veterinary Council), training institutions (e.g., universities, veterinary schools), government training programs

Research and Innovation	National Research Foundation (NRF) - Pretoria	Wildlife Research Centers - Various locations across South Africa	Research institutions, researchers, international organizations (e.g., WHO, WOAH)
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Anthrax endemic areas of South Africa

Province/Region	Endemic Areas	Characteristics and Factors
Limpopo	Private game reserves and conservation areas	Anthrax outbreaks observed among wildlife populations; linked to environmental factors and interactions between wildlife, livestock, and humans
Kruger National Park	Within the park	Sporadic outbreaks among wildlife species, including buffalo, elephants, and antelopes; ecological dynamics contribute to the persistence of anthrax
Northern Cape	Rural and agricultural areas	Anthrax outbreaks reported among livestock and wildlife populations; factors such as climate and soil conditions influence anthrax occurrence

3. Resources for surveillance of anthrax in humans in South Africa

3.1 [National Institute for Communicable Diseases¹⁰](#)

The NICD, a division of the National Health Laboratory Service (NHLS), plays a central role in the surveillance, diagnosis, and response to infectious diseases, including anthrax. It coordinates with provincial health departments, veterinary authorities, and other stakeholders to monitor anthrax activity, provide diagnostic support, and facilitate outbreak investigations.

3.2 [Notifiable Medical Conditions \(NMC\) Disease List¹¹](#)

Anthrax is a Category 1 Notifiable Medical condition, requiring immediate reporting by the most rapid means available upon diagnosis followed by a written or electronic notification to the Department of Health within 24 hours of diagnosis by health care providers, private health laboratories or public health laboratories

3.3 [Draft Guidelines on Management and Control of Human Anthrax in South Africa 2018¹²](#)

This comprehensive document contains descriptions of the disease and its forms, incidence, epidemiology, diagnosis, treatment, recommended response to suspected exposure, and contact details by province.

3.4 National Health Act¹³

The National Health Act 61 of 2003 provides a framework for a structured uniform health system within South Africa, considering laws governing national, provincial and local governments regarding health services. There are many regulations included in the act, including the Minister having the overall responsibility to oversee the implementation of these Regulations. The Director -General (**DG**) is mandated to promote adherence to the use of standard case definitions for all notifiable medical conditions according to the WHO International Classification of Diseases as adapted by the national department. The DG must also: promote adherence to the use of national department forms and tools for reporting notifiable medical conditions; promote the adherence to the notification procedures stipulated in these Regulations; ensure that structures, processes and systems are in place for the surveillance and control of notifiable medical conditions as stipulated in national department guidelines; designate and ensure the functioning of the National IHR Focal Point; notify the WHO IHR Contact Point through the National IHR Focal Point within 24 hours of epidemiological assessment, of all events which may constitute a public health emergency of international concern; and issue and promote adherence to national department guidelines on the surveillance and control of notifiable medical conditions.

The Provincial Member of the Executive Council responsible for health must ensure the implementation of these Regulations within the Province. The district health manager must implement these Regulations within his or her district. The sub -district health manager must implement these Regulations within his or her health sub-district. The health establishment manager must implement these Regulations within his or her health establishment. The regulations state that a health care provider must: notify the focal person at the health sub -district level of any diagnosed case of a notifiable medical condition using standard case definitions for notifiable medical conditions according to the WHO international Classification of Diseases as adapted by the national department. The provider must also use national department forms and tools for reporting notifiable medical conditions as well as notification procedures stipulated in these Regulations. They must ensure adherence to these Regulations; and adhere to national department guidelines on the surveillance and control of notifiable medical conditions.

The regulations stipulate that a laboratory manager must ensure: that these Regulations are adhered to in his or her laboratory; adherence to the use of standard case definitions for notifiable medical conditions according to the WHO International Classification of Diseases as adapted by the national department; adherence to the use of national department forms and tools for reporting notifiable medical conditions; adherence to the notification procedures stipulated in these Regulations; and that national department guidelines on the surveillance and control of notifiable medical conditions are adhered to and implementation. Pathologists and laboratory personnel must: notify the focal person at the health sub -district level of any diagnosed case of a notifiable medical condition using standard case definitions for notifiable medical conditions according to the WHO International Classification of Diseases as adapted by the national department. They must use national department forms and tools for reporting notifiable medical conditions, adhere to the notification procedures stipulated in these Regulations; ensure adherence to these Regulations; and adhere to national department guidelines on the surveillance and control of notifiable medical conditions.

The notification and reporting process mandated by the Act involves multiple stakeholders. A health care provider who diagnoses a patient with a notifiable medical condition listed in Annexure A, Table 1, must report the medical condition to the focal person at the health sub -district level by the most rapid means available upon diagnosis, even before the case is laboratory confirmed to facilitate the implementation of public health measures and response. The report completed in sub -regulation must be followed by a

written or electronic notification within 24 hours of diagnosis, to facilitate the implementation of public health measures and response. A health care provider who diagnoses a patient with a notifiable medical condition listed in Annexure A, Table 2, must notify the focal person at the health sub -district level of the medical condition within seven days of diagnosis, through a written or electronic notification, to facilitate the implementation of public health measures and response. If a health care provider treats a patient and they die, the death must be reported to the sub-district by the most rapid means, followed by a written or electronic notification within 24 hours of death.

3.5 The National Health Amendment Act 12 of 2013¹⁴

This act served to establish the Office of Health Standards Compliance.

MOZAMBIQUE

1. Overview

With a GDP of \$1,291 US dollars per capita in 2018 (World Development Indicators-WDI), Mozambique is one of the ten poorest countries in the world: about 62% of the population lives in poverty earning less than \$1.90 international dollars/day (2014). There are resources for identifying and reporting anthrax and other zoonotic diseases, and there are regulations in place describing the responsible authorities for surveillance, reporting, and responding to disease outbreaks. However, documents cited in this report indicate insufficient implementation of surveillance and disease control by international standards. In March of 2024, Mozambique announced an anthrax vaccination campaign aimed at stopping the spread of the disease in cattle in the central part of the country.²⁴

2. Resources for surveillance of anthrax in animals in Mozambique

2.1 Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MADER)¹⁵

The Ministry (**MADER**) website has an Animal Health drop-down menu with a section on epidemiological monitoring, indicating that surveillance allows early detection of outbreaks and timely measures to stop the disease and that a surveillance system for animal disease has been established at the National Directorate of Veterinary Services (**DINAV**). There is a [Manual do Campo](#) for diagnosis of animal diseases on the website. This document is written in Portuguese and intended for animal health surveillance professionals. It provides specific instructions to: check the contents of the “Action-Aid kit;” check that the cold elements are properly frozen; to arrange a time with the breeder to investigate the occurrence; examine the animal and make a presumptive diagnosis; inform the breeder of the presumptive diagnosis; provide information regarding the disease; provide expectations regarding confirmation of the diagnosis; detail any precautions that should be taken in case of a zoonosis and/or for the movement of animals prior to receiving the final diagnosis. If a notifiable disease is suspected, authorities are required to search for the necessary information about movement of animals to and from the farm; follow all script noted in the Animal Health Regulations in force in Mozambique; and inform the breeder about the next steps (e.g., make a return visit to the farm; take a sick or dead animal to the lab for necropsy; conduct lab tests; and notify breeder of any costs that will be incurred. In such instances, there is minimal information required, including: the district, local, and name of the owner of the animal; animal species involved and other species in contact; type of production and feeding system; total number of animals in the pack and the number of sick and dead animals; data from the first observation of the problem; clinical signs observed; any vaccinations and treatments including the type; and any recent movement of animals).

The regulations provide lists of necessary supplies and equipment for sample collection, storage, and transport are provided, including PPE and storage media for some samples. The regulations stipulate that if visiting infected and non-infected examinations on the same day, technicians must obey the following rules: avoid visiting non-infected and potentially infected after work; decontaminate and disinfect boots, possessions, clothing, equipment between visits; minimize contamination of the environment by doing necropsies on top of a plastic canvas, which should be washed and disinfected after work; do not use needles on more than an animal without sterilization; and wash and disinfect or ferment for 20 minutes. The regulations’ website lists specific diseases (with photos) are covered with regard to: general characteristics of the disease; clinical signs; susceptible species; source of infection; zoonotic potential; tests available; differential diagnoses; prevention; and asymptomatic carriers. The diseases of interest covered

include: foot and mouth disease; Rift Valley Fever; Peste des Petit Ruminants; African Swine Fever; Newcastle Disease; Trypanosomiasis; and Helminth disease. The MADER site also lists Mandatory Vaccinations, including for anthrax. The Mozambique Animal Vaccination Campaign launched on April 3, 2024. The campaign aims to immunize animals against notifiable diseases, in defense of Public Health, and will vaccinate 10,524 cattle against anthrax. The MADER website recommends vaccinating all cattle over 4 months of age for anthrax annually between April and July. It explains that vaccination is necessary to achieve herd immunity to prevent the entry of the disease into the population, and that studies indicate that vaccination is effective when at least 80% of the population at risk develops neutralizing antibodies in high concentrations most of the time.

2.2 National Directorate of Veterinary Services (DINAV)¹⁶

The Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (**MASA**) was created pursuant to Resolution 4/2015 of the Council of Ministers (MASA Statute). DINAV is one of five directorates in MASA and is structured into Administration, Planning and Legislation sections, and five departments: Epidemiology; Disease Prevention and Control; Tsetse Fly Control; Veterinary Public Health; and Wildlife Disease.

DINAV has primary responsibility and authority to regulate matters in the veterinary domain. Its' specific competencies are set forth in Article 9.1 of the MASA Statute, and include:

- Prepare, implement, monitor and evaluate policies, strategies and legislation in animal production and health.
- Protect animal health, including aquatic animals and sanitary control of products of animal origin.
- Establish surveillance mechanisms for the prevention, control and eradication of animal disease.
- Collaborate with regional and international organizations on epidemiological surveillance.
- Collect, process, and analyze data.
- Promote partnership with the private sector.
- Promote livestock production, processing and trade and funding.
- Implement animal health and animal welfare protection measures.
- Implement veterinary certification.
- Enforce compliance with legislation on animal production and health and exercise authority as the competent authority.
- Define and implement programs and management of animal genetic resources in the country.
- Conduct other activities relevant to the terms of the MASA Statute and other applicable legislation.

2.3 Veterinary Legislation Support Program¹⁶

This document, produced by WOA in 2015, was a report of the Veterinary Legislation Identification Mission for the Republic of Mozambique. The following is excerpted from this report. The objectives of the VLSP Mission were to raise awareness of the importance of veterinary legislation for modern, effective operation of the veterinary services, review the principles for developing high-quality veterinary legislation and review the status of the Member's legislation relative to the OIE standards for veterinary legislation. It also studied the context of the agriculture sector in the country, which is dominated by smallholder farmers and characterized by low productivity, limited infrastructure and investment, and poor market access.

Additional constraints on the livestock sector include a weak network of veterinary services and a lack of infrastructure and resources. It found that there was virtually no legislation on some key elements, including veterinary laboratories, animal welfare, and veterinary medicines and biologicals (legislation on the latter is jointly being developed by the DINAV and counterparts at the Ministry of Health). A related

concern, which was also expressed by nearly every stakeholder, is the weak chain of command from central to local level, in large part due to the transfer of district level veterinary services out of MASA authority and into Mozambique Veterinary Legislation Identification Mission-2015 via local administrative units under Law N° 8/2003, as approved by the National Assembly.

The lack of a strong vertical command hinders the VA's ability to control animal disease in the country, particularly in the case of transboundary animal disease outbreaks where early detection and rapid and effective response are critical. Most of the enabling provisions are inadequate, leaving the authorities without an explicit legal mandate to discharge their responsibilities. Poor drafting weakens many of the powers and responsibilities that are conferred, for example, undermining accountability by using the passive voice. A lack of complementarity and harmonization among related instruments further limits their effectiveness. A serious concern is the absence of a formal chain of command, which weakens the VA's capacity for animal disease detection and control, particularly in the case of transboundary animal disease outbreaks where rapid and effective response at every administrative level is critical. There is no formal disease surveillance system or communication protocol to enable early detection and control and reporting of animal disease occurrences. Finally, there is a dearth of secondary legislation setting out the technical, procedural and administrative modalities for implementing the primary legislation. Considering the findings and conclusions of this report, the WOA Team recommended the following steps be taken to reform the legislative framework for veterinary matters in Mozambique (excerpted from the report):

1. Suspend the current process of preparing a new Animal Health Regulation for enactment.
2. Elaborate an overall legislative strategy for all elements of the veterinary domain before drafting or amending specific pieces of legislation. In that process, attention should be paid to legislative hierarchy; harmonization and complementarity among different instruments; choice of matters for primary vs. secondary legislation; treatment of areas with distinct regulatory regimes, such as veterinary medicines and biologicals, under separate instruments.
3. Consider building the legislative strategy around an animal health and disease control law to provide the appropriate legislative foundation for necessary VA powers vis-à-vis private citizens where constitutional rights are at issue as well as local authorities on matters of decentralization and chain of command.
4. Collaborate with other authorities that have competencies in or related to the veterinary domain. Carefully articulate the division of responsibilities and modalities for communication and coordination. Resolve any conflicts in the relevant legislation, including between the organic statutes of MASA and the Ministry of Fisheries concerning aquatic animals.
5. Develop individual instruments, considering the findings and recommendations of this report. During that process, outline the contents of the relevant subsidiary legislation to ensure all areas are covered and to help determine the placement of specific provisions. Extend the stakeholder consultation process to authorities and other actors at local level.
6. Define the institutional framework for veterinary services taking a holistic, system-based approach that provides the central authorities with the overall competence to develop programs and implement activities throughout the territory; assigns specific areas of responsibility to provincial and local authorities; defines the relationship between the different administrative levels and provides for coordination mechanisms to ensure coherent and effective implementation on the ground.
7. Provide for a formal chain of command along with mechanisms to coordinate and enforce implementation among different Veterinary Service (**VS**) actors. Examples range from holding joint planning and budgeting sessions to undertaking needs identification and awareness-raising workshops for staff at different administrative levels.

8. Train MASA staff and lawyers on the principles of legislative drafting to increase awareness, understanding and participation in the development of new legislation.

2.4 Decree No. 26/2009 approving the Regulation on Animal Health¹⁷

Like the regulatory documents listed for South Africa, this legislation approves the Regulation on Animal Health. Unlike the South African document, it is written in Portuguese and difficult to translate in its entirety. The Regulation, consisting of 124 articles and 1 Table is divided into 10 Chapters and regulates the sanitary norms to carry out epidemiological controls on animal diseases in all the territory of Mozambique.

The Regulation gives the MASA the competence to create complementary regulation on the issue and its objective is to establish norms for the epidemiological surveillance and control of animal diseases in Mozambique. Aimed at the protection of public health and livestock exports' market, it identifies the competent authorities and rules on conditions and requirements for import, transport and circulation of livestock and derived products. It regulates certification procedures, animal health measures and management of diseases. Finally, it regulates control measures for products of animal origin and wildlife animals. Particular attention is paid to the regulation of communication requirements and to the definition of applicable penalties.

The Regulation is organized into sections including definitions and objectives; import, circulation and transportation of animals; provisions for sanitary control; sanitary measures and declaration of diseases; sanitary measures for wildlife; controls on animal products and for veterinary uses; administrative procedures and sanctions; general provisions; and an annex listing in detail all fines to be paid for illegal activities. While the Regulation on Animal Health specifically mentions zoonotic disease surveillance and control, it does not specify diseases.

3. Resources for surveillance of anthrax in humans in Mozambique

3.1 Ministry of Health (MISAU)¹⁸

The responsibilities of the Ministry of Health (**MISAU**) include, but are not limited to: promotion of universal access to health care; proposing legislation, policies, strategies and actions necessary for the implementation, execution, monitoring and evaluation of the National Health Policy; ensuring regulation, supervision and inspection regarding the activities and provision of healthcare; promoting the expansion of access to healthcare; promoting the prevention and control of endemic and epidemic diseases; promoting and developing innovation in appropriate health technologies, particularly in the areas of health infrastructure, health technologies, pharmaceutical products and medical devices; promoting guidance of the development of human resources training in the specific technical-professional area of health; promoting development of health research at different levels of care; and managing the Health Information System. In the area of epidemiological information systems, the Ministry of Health has the power to both ensure the functioning of the epidemiological information system for detecting notifiable diseases and others; and use, in an operational manner, the epidemiological information produced, maintain and increase the exchange of this information with countries in the region and international health organizations.

The National Directorate of Public Health is responsible for establishing and maintaining an epidemiological information system for detecting notifiable diseases, as well as to implement rapid response center for

epidemics and other emergencies. Under the National Directorate of Public Health are the Department of Health Surveillance and the Department of Disease Prevention and Control. These departments do not have websites for additional information. The MISAU website contains many documents regarding health policy and strategy. Comprehensive understanding of these reports is compromised by the fact that they are published in Portuguese and difficult to translate in their entirety. The 2019 Report on Mortality and Causes of Death in Mozambique presents information about monitoring the occurrence of events in the community was carried out by Community Surveillance Agents (**CSAs**) who were recruited by INE in consultation with the Agents Program Multipurpose Elementary (**APE**) from the Ministry of Health, technicians from the District Services of Health, Women and Social Action and community leaders. During the first 2-3 months after deployment, all CSAs were instructed to visit all households in your areas to list household members, family member and collect additional information about age, sex, degree of kinship with the head of household and habitual residence status (resident or visitor). In each province, autopsy investigators were recruited and trained by INE and INS. Much of the surveillance program appears to have been supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and there are no mentions of anthrax in the report.

The SIS-MA is MISAU's main data management system based on DHIS2, which is an open-source web-based software for supporting public health information collection, analysis, visualization and dissemination. The Epidemiological Surveillance Information System (**SIVE**) is a SIS-MA module designed to collect, analyze and interpret epidemiological data in real time, allowing a rapid and effective response to disease outbreaks, as well as recording data from vaccination campaigns against diseases of surveillance. A Death Registration Information System (**SIS-ROH**) was implemented in 2009 in General, Provincial, District and Rural Hospitals, at country level, having been replaced later by the Hospital Management System (**SIS-HOSP**) in the 2010s.

3.2 Joint External Evaluation of IHR Core Capacities of the Republic of Mozambique, 2016¹⁹

CDC's Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (**IDSR**) program conducted international training including in Mozambique between 1980 and 2020, and created Technical Guidelines for IDSR Training Modules, particularly for those diseases targeted by the [International Health Regulations](#) (WHO). In April 2016, the WHO conducted a week-long assessment of the International Health Regulations Core Capacities in Mozambique to determine current strengths, areas for strengthening, and priority actions. In the area of real-time disease surveillance and reporting, Mozambique received peer review scores of 2-3/5: The evaluation found that "There is no comprehensive, well-coordinated legal framework to address all issues relevant to the IHR (2005), and therefore, developing a public health law to address the remaining gaps is a priority. The overall recommendations of the evaluation were:

1. Complete comprehensive review of existing national legislation, across sectors, in line with One Health.
2. Complete the development and drafting of a public health law.
3. Strengthen communication and advocacy with stakeholders regarding the necessity for the new public health law; the positive impacts it will have on public health; and at the appropriate time, how it will be implemented with stakeholders.
4. Review and strengthen enforcement of existing public health laws.

One of the strengths of the program was that the National Institute of Health runs two macro-projects to support surveillance and response that can support adjustments of legislation and policies. The evaluation identified an opportunity for structuring a unit for early review of the information generated by national surveillance system. It also identified an opportunity for additional research into, and control of, outbreaks and health emergencies. Regarding zoonotic diseases, the evaluation reported that in animal health, under-

reporting of zoonosis in the country represents a serious concern as veterinary and human surveillance systems are weak and mostly passive due to the involvement of slaughterhouses and large-scale farmers. It also recognized low levels of awareness on zoonotic threats at programmatic and community levels exacerbates the under-reporting. There are few veterinarians in the public sector (138 in the entire country) serving the community. To these ends, additional recommendations included:

1. Develop a One Health strategy for joint operations and coordination among the different key sectors of animal, human and wildlife health
2. Establish a National Surveillance Strategy framework for data-sharing among the key sectors.
3. Include animal or wildlife health professionals in the Field Epidemiology and Laboratory Training Programme (**FELTP**) that currently only trains human health personnel

Areas needing strengthening were identified, including a data-sharing strategy for zoonotic diseases between sectors and an establishment of One Health plan/strategy and task force that should be done as soon as possible. Limited capacity exists for outbreak investigation and response for zoonotic diseases in both human and animal health sector. Further, protocols and SOPs are needed for outbreak investigation and response for zoonotic diseases that are lacking.

3.3 One health Zoonotic Disease Prioritization for Multisectoral Engagement in Mozambique²⁰

In April of 2018, this 2-day workshop was held in Maputo. Participating organizations included the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Land, Environment, and Rural Development, Ministry of Sea, Inland Waters, Fisheries (**MIMAIP**), National Fish Inspection Institute (**INIP**), Faculty of Veterinary Medicine (**FAVET**), Eduardo Mondlane University (**UEM**), Directorate of Animal Sciences, National Museum of Natural History (**NMNH**), Order of Physicians of Mozambique, WHO, Mozambique, WOA, Mozambique, National Public Health Institute (**NPHI**), U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (**CDC**), and United States Agency for International Development (**USAID**), Mozambique. The purpose of the workshop was to identify zoonotic diseases of greatest national concern for Mozambique with equal representation of human, livestock, environment, wildlife, research and higher education sectors. The prioritized zoonotic diseases for Mozambique are rabies virus, zoonotic tuberculosis, salmonellosis, zoonotic avian influenza virus, trypanosomiasis, brucellosis, and Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever. Zoonotic diseases were ranked in importance based on disease occurrence on a regional and local level, and pandemic or epidemic potential; morbidity and mortality; capacity of laboratory diagnostics and epidemiological surveillance; availability of resources and mechanisms for collaboration, prevention, treatment, and eradication of the disease; and social-economic and environmental impact. Based on these criteria and using a semi-quantitative scoring system developed by WHO, anthrax ranked 12th in importance as a zoonotic disease in Mozambique. Some of the recommendations made because of this workshop included:

1. Developing a zoonoses surveillance manual in the One Health approach.
2. Preparing and implementing the Standard Operational Procedures and Protocols for General Surveillance and Response, and Priority Diseases.
3. Hiring a consultancy for the design and implementation of the online platform for analysis and data sharing.
4. Defining the tools for mapping high-risk areas of the most important diseases.
5. Carrying out expeditions of research on the occurrence of priority diseases and their reservoirs

Specific recommended next steps included the MISAU sending out an invitation to coordinate the One Health Committee among the present ministries at the workshop; integrating additional ministries into International Health Regulations planning; and coordinating the implementation of the activities described in Global Health Security Agenda. Next steps for the MADER included identifying appropriate points of contact within the ministry to be involved in the One Health committee; strengthening the surveillance system for zoonotic diseases in wildlife; and implementing pilot studies for zoonotic disease in areas of conservation with high occurrence of zoonotic diseases.

3.4 [The Global Health Security Index 2021](#)²³

This document provides evaluation of Mozambique’s capabilities in prevention, early detection and reporting, response and mitigation of disease events, among other measures of capacity in the management of vulnerability to biological threats. Regarding zoonotic disease risk, the Index cites Decree number 26 of 2009 as a national law on animal health, in particular zoonotic disease. However, it points out that “the [OIE PVS report of 2015](#) stated that, while the legislation exists, its implementation is ineffective.” Regarding surveillance for zoonotic disease, the Index reports there is insufficient evidence that Mozambique has any laws or guidelines for the surveillance of many zoonotic pathogens. Another conclusion is that there is not sufficient evidence for the existence of a department or agency that functions across ministries and is dedicated to zoonotic disease. The report recohere is no evidence of a national mechanism for livestock to report on disease surveillance to a central government agency. The website for the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security does not provide a link or contact for livestock owners to report diseases. There is insufficient evidence that Mozambique conducts surveillance of zoonotic diseases in wildlife. The number of veterinarians per 100,000 people was 1.26.

Summary of institutional resources in Mozambique

Institution	Type	Location
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MADER)	Government	Maputo
National Institute of Health (INS)	Government	Maputo
National Directorate of Veterinary Services (DINAV)	Government	Maputo, Provincial Directorates
Provincial Health Directorates	Government	Various provinces in Mozambique
Mozambican Veterinary Association (AMV)	Non-Governmental	Nationwide
National Veterinary Research Institute (INIVE)	Government	Maputo
National Public Health Laboratory (LNSP)	Government	Maputo
Provincial Veterinary Laboratories	Government	Various provinces in Mozambique
Provincial Epidemiology Units	Government	Various provinces in Mozambique
Research Institutions	Government	Nationwide

Wildlife Conservation Organizations	Non-Governmental	Gorongosa National Park, Niassa National Reserve, Quirimbas National Park, Bazaruto Archipelago National Park, other protected areas
Provincial and Municipal Governments	Government	Various provinces and municipalities in Mozambique
Ministry of Land, Environment, and Rural Development (MITADER)	Government	Maputo
Wildlife Conservation NGOs	Non-Governmental	Various locations across Mozambique
Veterinary Training Institutions (e.g., University Veterinary Faculties)	Governmental	Various provinces in Mozambique
Human Health Training Institutions (e.g., Medical Schools)	Government	Nationwide
Wildlife and Environmental Education Centers	Non-Governmental	Various locations across Mozambique
Interdisciplinary Task Forces	Government	Nationwide
Stakeholder Engagement Groups	Non-Governmental	Nationwide
National Research Institute (INIC)	Government	Maputo
Wildlife Research Centers	Non-Governmental	Various locations across Mozambique

Endemic anthrax areas in Mozambique

Province	Endemic Areas	Characteristics and Factors
Gaza	Rural and agricultural areas	Anthrax outbreaks reported among livestock and wildlife populations; influenced by environmental conditions such as soil composition and seasonal flooding
Maputo	Rural and peri-urban settings	Anthrax cases observed among livestock and wildlife; livestock farming practices and wildlife interactions contribute to the persistence of anthrax
Zambezia	Rural and remote areas	Anthrax outbreaks recorded among livestock and wildlife populations; environmental factors such as soil alkalinity and seasonal weather patterns influence anthrax distribution

General resources available regarding anthrax control and surveillance

World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH)²⁴

WOAH provides a description of anthrax in the terrestrial code and terrestrial manual. The terrestrial manual summarizes detection and diagnostic techniques and vaccine information, including intended use and methods of manufacturing. The terrestrial code describes recommendations for managing health risks associated with anthrax by describing and offering links for the recommended procedures for importing ruminants, equids, pigs, and the following products from these species: fresh meat and meat products for human consumption; hides, skins, and hair; wool; milk and milk products; and bristles from pigs. The terrestrial code also provides procedures for the inactivation of *B. anthracis* spores in bone and protein meal, wool and hair.

Guidelines for the Surveillance and Control of Anthrax in Human and Animals, 3rd ed.¹¹²⁵

A thorough resource produced by the World Health Organization but not related specifically to surveillance procedures or capacity in South Africa or Mozambique.

International Health Regulations (IHR) 2005²⁶

Developed by the WHO, the IHR provide a legal framework defining the rights and responsibilities of 196 member countries in handling public health events and emergencies with the potential to spread to neighboring countries. The IHR require that all countries can detect, assess, report, and respond to public health risks and emergencies.

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